

HISTO-MRI Project

This project has received funding from the European Union's H2020 Programme under grant agreement no 737180— HISTO-MRI

D1.3: Dissemination Plan

Version	Date	Reviewer

Table of contents

1	Deliverable description	4
2	Introduction	4
3	Dissemination Strategy.....	4
4	Dissemination Tools	5
4.1	Logo	5
4.2	Web Site.....	5
4.3	Templates (letters, digital presentations...)	6
4.4	Brochures.....	6
4.5	Posters	7
4.6	Video.....	7
5	Dissemination Activities	7
5.1	Publications	7
5.2	Press releases	7
5.3	Conferences and workshops	7

1 Deliverable description

This deliverable describes the strategy of the consortium for the dissemination of the project results.

This deliverable is the result of *Task 5*, part of **WP1 – Management**.

2 Introduction

The main objective of the dissemination is to generate awareness of the results of the Project, maximizing its social and economical impact.

In particular, the specific objectives are:

- To raise awareness among the different target groups.
- To engage the scientific community, stimulating the debate about the Project, getting input/feedback from the community.
- To promote the exploitable outputs and results of the project.

To achieve these objectives, the Consortium will collaborate in the definition of the message, the target groups and a roadmap of dissemination activities.

3 Dissemination Strategy

The Dissemination and Exploitation Committee (**DEC**) will act as the coordinator of all dissemination related issues. It will be in charge of the creation a revision of the Dissemination Plan that will be approved by the General Assebmly (**GA**). Some actions have already been identified: A website; Publication in high profile refereed journals; Press releases; Participation in international conferences, workshops and in association with other European projects; conferences.

Every partner in the Consortium is encouraged to disseminate all the relevant knowledge generated in the project. Considering that some results of the project will be exploitable (by the SMEs in the Consortium) no dissemination action will be made if it affects negatively to the protection of IP. To avoid this, any potential publication of knowledge will be notified previously to the DEC for its approval. These procedures will be detailed in the Consortium Agreement.

The partners already identified key target groups for dissemination. The Board will ensure that the Dissemination and Awareness campaign of the project reaches the following groups:

- The General Public through patient organizations and industrial associations;
- The International Scientific community as for example the ISMRM (International Society for Magnetic Resonance in Medicine), ESMRMB (European Society for Magnetic Resonance in Medicine and Biology),...
- The Clinicians, through different clinical networks;
- The Health and Education Professionals;
- The stakeholders working in the field of medical imaging, aerospace, automotive and food Industries.

4 Dissemination Tools

The consortium will create different tools that will be used by all the members in their dissemination activities.

4.1 Logo

A dedicated logo has been created. It will be used in all dissemination material to be used.

4.2 Web Site

A dedicated web site has been created to explain the project aims and objectives, as well as providing general information about HISTO-MRI project activities and the results achieved. This is part of the project communication activities and the strategy of the HISTO-MRI consortium for spreading information about the project. The address of the website is: www.histo-mri-i3m.upv.es.

In situ imaging of living tissues with cellular spatial resolution

Coordinator: José M. BENLLOCH
Project Number: 737180

The main objective of HISTO-MRI project is to develop the technologies that will enable the non-invasive visualization of individual human cells in vivo and in real time, based on a radical new Magnetic Resonance Imaging concept: High Frequency Pulsed MRI. To accomplish this ambitious objective, several new challenging multidisciplinary technologies will have to be developed: 1) new method for the production of magnet

4.3 Templates (letters, digital presentations...)

The Consortium will define all the communication instruments, using the logotypes of the HISTO-MRI project, the EC H2020 and the partners, including templates for: letters; slide presentations; press releases. This will allow a uniform appearance, providing basic information about the project.

4.4 Brochures

The Consortium will design a brochure containing the main information about the project. The objectives of the brochure are:

- to inform the scientific and medical community about the results of the project,
- to inform patients about the results of the project,
- to attract potential users of the results of the project.

The brochure will be created in English and will be distributed to the partners that will participate in dissemination activities where a high number of attendees is expected: conferences, workshops, exhibitions, etc..

4.5 Posters

The Consortium will create several posters about the HISTO-MRI project. Their design will depend on the dissemination activity. They may focus in the technical results of the project or the clinical results.

4.6 Video

The dissemination plan includes a video production by the end of the second year of the project. The video will contain a short description of the project and its objectives highlighting the technical innovation and the research activities able to represent the scientific value of the project.

5 Dissemination Activities

The Dissemination and Exploitation Committee (DEC) will act as the coordinator of all dissemination activities.

5.1 Publications

Publication on the HISTO-MRI results to achieve their rapid dissemination in high profile refereed journals once appropriated national or international protection have been obtained for them. The Consortium will analyse the impact of the publications, reviewing the number of cites through online tools like Web of Science or SCOPUS. To this end, the results will be divulgated to the following, as appropriate:

- to other Partners in the network;
- to the Partners' own administrations;
- to the European Commission;
- to the scientific and medical communities;
- to the medical Imaging and biomarker industry;
- to the concerned patients' associations;
- to the aerospace, automotive and food industry;
- by submission of collaborative research articles;

5.2 Press releases

The consortium will promote the publication of press releases through important international agencies like Reuters. CSIC will make use of its communication department to contact the Spanish media. The rest of the partners will contact the media at national level to publish press releases.

5.3 Conferences and workshops

Participation in the appropriate international conferences, workshops and in association with other European projects: conferences (Annual meeting of the ISMRM, ESMRMB, SPIE Medical Imaging), forums and workshops (two will be organized: one on month 18, to show the results achieved and to collect the input from specialists; one on month 36, to show the final results of the project), for specialists but also those open to the general public. For each event, the Consortium will review the number and type of attendees to analyse its impact.